

EVALUATION OF THE ELASTIC ENERGY RELEASE RATES OF TRANSVERSE AND DELAMINATION CRACKS IN [0/90] CARBON-EPOXY SYMMETRIC LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

The Boundary Element Method (BEM) and the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) are used in numerical analysis to evaluate the Energy Release Rate (ERR) of a transverse crack and of a delamination crack in a $[0/90]_s$ carbon-epoxy laminate loaded in tension. Numerical results are corroborated with experimental observations.

Keywords: Energy Release Rate, CFRP, transverse crack, delamination crack

INTRODUCTION

Although in general laminates include plies predominantly oriented 0° with respect to the dominant load direction, it is usually necessary to include some plies oriented at 90° so that the composite can have some strength in the transverse direction. Consequently, in a laminate of this kind there are adjacent plies oriented 90° to each other. The presence in a laminate of plies oriented 90° with respect to the preferred direction of load generates almost immediately the appearance of microcracks transverse to the load (parallel to fibers in the 90° ply). The coalescence of these microcracks leads to the appearance of a transverse macrocrack that is assumed to arrest when it reaches the interface with a 0° ply, due to the presence of fibers perpendicular to this crack. This may initiate single or double deflection of the crack, which then propagates as a delamination crack. These phenomena have been comprehensively reviewed in [1], where many relevant contributions to the understanding of different aspects of the above damage mechanisms can be found.

BEM [2] has proved to be an effective numerical tool solving problems where singularities and/or contact between surfaces are encountered. This is the reason for its use in [3], where a very refined study of the stress state associated with the transverse and delamination crack (correcting formerly published results) has been done. An accurate determination of the stress distribution allows us to have confidence in the ERR values (computed using these distributions and VCCT [4]) and support the conclusions obtained in the analysis.

Additionally some specimens have been made and tested in tension, and images have been obtained of the damage using microscopical techniques. The experimental work corroborates the numerical predictions and identifies additional aspects.

NUMERICAL MODEL

The following thermoelastic parameters have been used in order to characterize the behaviour of the material: $E_{11} = 141.3$ MPa, $E_{22} = E_{33} = 9.58$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3$, $\nu_{23} = 0.32$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 5$ GPa, $G_{23} = 3.5$ GPa, $\alpha_{11} = -10^{-6}$, $\alpha_{13} = \alpha_{23} = 26 \cdot 10^{-6}$, 1 being the fibre direction and 3 the normal to the ply direction.

A 2D model has been used under the Generalized Plane Strain hypothesis. This model is easy to develop and analyse and could be applied to any xy plane, see Figure 1, of the specimen far enough of the laminate edges. The analysis of what happens in the neighbourhood of an edge is a very difficult problem, and requires a full 3D analysis.

Figure 1: Coordinate system and 2D model of the laminate.

The reference load has been a nominal axial strain $\varepsilon_{yy} = 0.01$, the free stress temperature being 100°C . Laminate Theory predicts for $\varepsilon_{yy} = 0.01$, $N_z = 0$ and $\Delta T = -100^\circ\text{C}$, the following results:

$$\varepsilon_{yy} = 0.01, \quad \varepsilon_{zz} = -0.0005, \quad N_y = 1686.57 \text{ N/mm}, \quad N_z = 0 \quad (1)$$

the other strains and stresses being null. It is assumed that ε_{yy} and ε_{zz} are fixed during the development of the damage.

Four general configurations, which are shown in Figure 2 (D being the distance between transverse cracks), are considered:

- The first one, Figure 2a, corresponds to an elementary cell between a complete transverse crack and a neighbouring transverse crack that is growing towards the interface.

- The second one, Figure 2b, corresponds to a double deflected delamination crack that initiates from a transverse crack tip that has reached the interface.
- The third one, Figure 2c, also corresponds to a double deflected delamination crack, but now growing towards a transverse crack that has already reached the interface, but has not initiated an associated delamination.
- The fourth one, Figure 2d, corresponds to an elementary cell including a non-completed transverse crack in the 90° lamina and a delamination crack along the interface between the two laminae.

Figure 2. Configurations analysed: (a) growth of a transverse crack, (b) symmetric growth of delamination cracks, (c) delamination crack growing towards a transverse crack that has previously reached the interface, and (d) interaction between transverse and delamination cracks (Cook-Gordon mechanism).

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Transverse Crack. Usually, the elementary cell used to study analytically the evolution of a transverse crack assumes that all transverse cracks, being far enough away from each other, grow together reaching at the same time the interface between laminae, [1]. Nevertheless, as experiments show that transverse cracks appear sequentially, the model shown in Figure 2a, is more realistic for the analysis of the process of transverse

cracking. However, [5, 6] show that differences are noteworthy only when the distance between two consecutive transverse cracks is small.

ERR evolution for different distances between transverse cracks, D , are shown in Figure 3, assuming a displacement controlled test. For $D > 4$ mm, the ERR curves are almost coincident, which means that interference between two consecutive transverse cracks is, for this case, small. When the distance between two consecutive transverse cracks is 2 mm (about twice the 90° ply thickness), the appearance and growth of a new intermediate crack requires a significant increase of the load.

However, the shape of the ERRs curves implies an initially unstable growth of the crack, which tends to arrest before reaching the interface. The remaining distance to the interface at which the crack arrests depends on the toughness of the material and on the size of the initial damage, and it might only be of about several fibre diameters [5]. This fact suggests that transverse cracking of the 90° ply is a sequential process.

Figure 3. Evolution of the ERR of a transverse crack for different distances between two consecutive transverse cracks (configuration shown in Figure 2a).

When a transverse crack nearly reaches the interface, the stress field at the tip of the crack affects the stresses along the interface. This is shown in Figure 4a, where traction distributions along the interface in front of a transverse crack that has not reached the interface are shown for three distances between consecutive transverse cracks, $D = 1, 2$ and 4 mm, and for two crack lengths, $a = 0.50$ and 0.54 mm.

When the crack approaches the interface, the normal tractions in the interface in front of the crack tip, and also their gradients, significantly increase. Nevertheless, as expected, it has almost no influence on the traction distribution in the vicinity of the neighbouring crack that has already reached the interface, Figure 4b.

It can also be observed in Figure 4 that stress distribution decreases if D is smaller, which means that the sooner a transverse crack appears, the greater is its capacity to generate damage, in general terms.

Figure 4. Normal stress along the interface: (a) in front of the growing transverse crack, and (b) close to the previous existing fully developed transverse crack.

Delamination crack. Figure 5 shows the ERR evolutions for delamination cracks corresponding to Figures 2b and 2c configurations. It can be clearly noticed how the evolutions differ when the size of the delamination crack increase, which can be understood by noticing the significant differences between the two configurations studied.

Nevertheless, for small delamination sizes, the evolutions predicted are quite similar, see Figure 6, significant differences appearing only when the delamination size reaches a critical value that depends on the distances between transverse cracks. Note also that the smaller the distance between transverse cracks, the smaller the ERR values, more load then being required to generate or grow delaminations. This means that transverse cracking prevents delamination, i.e. if for some reason there are two zones in the same laminate with different levels of transverse cracking density, more delamination damage will appear in the zone where the transverse cracks are more widely separated.

Interaction between an incomplete transverse crack and an incipient delamination crack. The traction distributions shown in Figure 4 could justify the appearance of damage at the interface even before the transverse crack had reached the interface, especially for the first transverse cracks to form. This situation is called the Cook-Gordon mechanism, Figure 2d configuration then being the appropriate one for the analysis. Figure 7 shows the evolution of ERR of the transverse crack, Figure 7a, and delamination, Figure 7b, for various combinations of a and D values.

The results corresponding to a transverse crack with different delamination crack lengths, show no significant changes except when the crack tip is so close to the

interface, that the use of a homogeneous approach is questionable. With reference to the delamination results, the delamination crack tends to arrest at a distance, from the plane containing the transverse crack, corresponding to about 5 fibre diameters. Both cracks, delamination and transverse, would grow stably, requiring more load to extend.

Figure 5. ERRs of the delamination crack for different transverse crack distances and configurations shown in Figures 2b and 2c.

Figure 6. ERR evolution for small delamination crack lengths.

Figure 7. ERR evolution for transverse and delamination cracks for the configuration shown in Figure 2d.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section a set of micro-photograph are shown and compared with numerical predictions.

The specimens used correspond to a carbon-epoxy composite (AS4/8552 HEXCEL) with a $[0_3/90_3]_S$ stacking sequence. The specimens have 100 mm of length (gauge length) and 25 mm of width. The thickness of each individual ply is 0.183 mm, the total thickness of the laminate being 2.2 mm. The curing temperature employed has been 177°C.

First of all, Figure 8 shows the order of distances found between transverse cracks.

Figure 8. General view of a cracked specimen.

Figure 9 shows a transverse crack that has stopped near the interface, the distance to it being similar to that predicted by the numerical analysis. The delamination-like damage,

observed by means of debonds appearing at the fiber/matrix interfaces closest to the tip of the transverse crack, can be also correlated with the numerical predictions.

Figure 9. (a) Transverse crack arrested near the interface, and (b) delamination-like damage along the interface.

It must be pointed out that for all transverse cracks analyzed, the aforementioned delamination-like damage along the interface has been detected. Figure 10 shows, as an example, a complete transverse crack and the incipient delamination in form of debonding. Note also that the distance along which debonding appears is about 5 fibres, which fits well with numerical predictions.

Figure 10. (a) Transverse crack stopped at the interface, and (b) like-delamination damage at the interface.

Finally, Figure 11 shows an alternative form of delamination-like damage. Thus, whereas in the former case the delamination-like damage appeared as debonds at the fibre/matrix interfaces in the 90° ply, on this occasion, the damage appears as debonding along the fibres of the 0° ply closest to the interface with the 90° ply. The appearance of one of these two types of delamination-like damage may prevent the appearance of the other, due to the associated stress release.

Figure 11. Like-delamination damage.

CONCLUSIONS

The damage process of a $[0/90]_s$ carbon-epoxy laminate loaded in tension has been analysed using the Boundary Element Method, numerical predictions having been corroborated experimentally. The developed Boundary Element models assume Generalized Plane Strain conditions, transverse in-plane strain being calculated from Laminate Theory. Thermal stresses caused by curing have been considered in the analysis.

Four damage configurations have been considered in order to analyse the transverse cracking process, the delamination process and the Cook-Gordon mechanism.

The configuration used to analyse the transverse cracking problem corresponds to a transverse crack growing between neighbouring transverse cracks that have already reached the interface. The ERR evolution for this transverse crack in the 90° ply shows that it would grow unstably until it is arrested near the interface with the 0° ply, but before reaching the interface. Numerical results predict that distance between the crack tip and the interface could be only about several fibres, it being corroborated by experimental results.

Two different configurations have been used in order to analyse the delamination between the 90° and the 0° plies. On one hand, the first configuration considers that delaminations grow in opposite directions from two neighbouring transverse crack tips. On the other hand, the second configuration considers that a delamination arises from a transverse crack tip and progresses towards the tip of the neighbour transverse crack, where no delamination has initiated. The initial evolution of the ERR for a delamination

crack is not anyway affected by the configuration considered and it shows an initial period of stable growth for delamination sizes up to about 5 fibre diameters, which has been corroborated by the experimental results.

Interactions between transverse and delamination cracks have shown that delamination damage would appear even before the transverse crack reaches the interface, and that the sooner the transverse cracks appears, the greater its capacity of generating damage. This fact has been corroborated with the experimental results, which have shown delamination-like damage at the interface in all the transverse cracks studied.

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